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DMP Writing Made Easy: A Hands-on Workshop for Chemists

Ann-Christin Andres & Fabian Fink | 21.01.2026

Introduction

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Introduction

Organisational aspects

Workshop rules

- Zoom
 - Mute your microphone if you are not speaking.
 - Turn your camera on 😊.
 - Raise your hand if you would like to say anything.
 - Raise your hand if you have any questions or write them in the chat. We will take care of your request immediately.
- Breakout rooms
 - Unmute your microphone.
 - After the scheduled time, leave the room and return to main room.
 - Or wait, you will be automatically redirected to the main room.

Time schedule

Time	Topic
09:00 - 09:30	Welcome, introduction to NFDI4Chem, and DMP basics
09:30 - 10:40	DMP Writing: Section 1 & 2
10:40 - 10:50	Coffee break
10:50 - 12:10	DMP Writing: Section 3 & 4
12:10 - 13:10	Lunch break
13:10 - 14:30	DMP Writing: Section 5 & 6
14:30 - 14:50	Wrap-up, NFDI4Chem services, and Q&A session

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Introduction

NFDI and NFDI4Chem

- Founded in 2018 – funded by federal government and states as part of federal government’s digitalisation strategy
- Main goal:
 - Improvement and creation of Research Data Infrastructure & Management
 - Provision of tools, trainings and initiation of cultural change
- 27 consortia (26 discipline-specific + Base4NFDI)
- 5 sections (metadata, infra, edutrain, ELSA, industry)

Figure: Adaptation of “NFDI Consortia” by [Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur \(NFDI\) e.V.](https://www.nfdi-research.org/) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) via [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/) (adaptation: translation)

NFDI4Chem – who are we?

NFDI4Chem: Focus on molecules

NFDI4Chem: Vision

NFDI4Chem: Data handling from creation to re-use

© F. Garg/ NFDI4Chem

Create Data
Smart Lab

Publish & Access Data
Repositories

© F. Garg/ NFDI4Chem

Find & Use Data
**Metadata, Semantics
& Standards**

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Get Support
Cultural Change

Who are we?

NFDI4Chem Task Area: Community and Training

Ann-Christin Andres
Johannes-Gutenberg-
University Mainz

Fabian Fink
RWTH Aachen
University

Dr. Annett Schröter
Friedrich Schiller
University Jena

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Introduction

Introduction of attendees

Introduction of attendees

- We would like to know more about you!
- Short poll:
 - Wait for the poll to start
 - Answer the questions

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Introduction

Data life cycle

Data life cycle

- Describes the lifespan of the data
- Based on various phases
- Different approaches to the same model depending on the institution, the funder, ...

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Introduction

FAIR principles

FAIR principles

- Published in 2016 by FORCE11
- Guidelines to enhance reusability of data
- Increasingly important in science
- Part of DFG “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice”

Figure: “Publications and Data” by [Auke Herrema](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [RDM Promotional Material](#)

- Not all Open Data are FAIR, not all FAIR data are necessarily open

Figure: Adaptation of “FAIR and Open” by [Sarah Jones](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [slideshare](#), accessed: 2025-12-05 (adaptation: colour and alignment)

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Data Management Plan

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Data Management Plan

Introduction

What is a Data Management Plan (DMP)?

A DMP describes the handling of research data during and after a research project, it is a formal and at the same time a living document.

Figure: "Data Management Plan" by [The Turing Way](#) & [Scriberia](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [Zenodo](#)

Elements of a DMP

Intellectual property rights

Archiving and preservation

Legal requirements

Quality assurance

Data description

Format

Responsibility

Existing data

Ethics and privacy

A DMP answers the W-questions:
WHAT data goes into a project (reuse) and comes out of it (potential reuse)?
HOW does the team take care of the data?

Audience

Metadata

WHO is allowed to do **WHAT** with the data **WHEN?**

Security

Budget

Storage and backup

Data organisation

Selection and retention periods

Access and sharing

Benefits of a DMP

- Supports the research process
- Supports FAIR data
- Saves time in the long term
- Offers continuity
- Helps to consider issues related to confidentiality, ethics, security and copyright

Checklist

Checklist must be submitted as part of proposal

1. Data description
2. Documentation and data quality
3. Storage and technical archiving the project
4. Legal obligations and conditions
5. Data exchange and long-term accessibility
6. Responsibility and resources

Released December 2021

Link to DFG checklist: [de/en](#) (accessed 2015-12-09)

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Data Management Plan

Tools

Chemistry-specific DMP template

- NFDI4Chem developed a chemistry-specific DFG checklist
 - Enriched with information
 - Possible answer options
 - One or more free text fields per question
- Approach:
 - Survey on chemistry-specific aspects
 - Interviews on chemistry-specific DMP in 2022 + 2023
- Template on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948510>
- Template is also available at [NFDI4Chem RDMO instance](#) (accessed 2025-12-09)

Chemistry-Specific Catalog: DFG Checklist

The present questionnaire is a checklist issued by the German Research Foundation (DFG), enriched with chemistry-specific content and supplemented with necessary questions for better understanding and completeness. The DFG checklist must be submitted with your application and at the project's completion and is intended to assist you in structuring your data management. If you have any questions, please contact the central Research Data Management (RDM) team at your university or research institution, or reach out to NFDI4Chem at helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de.

The following questions are for describing chemical datasets generated and/or used in the project. The definition of what constitutes a dataset is an important conceptual decision that must be made individually for each institute or project. Choose a logical unit of your research data as a dataset, to which the same information regarding methodology, technology, accessibility, etc., applies. This can be, for example, a molecule, synthesis steps, the employed analysis method, similar simulation calculations, etc.

Categorising data into datasets helps assess the value of the data in terms of potential reuse and subsequent archiving. Since all questions must be answered for each individual dataset, an overly granular structure is not practical. Some aspects of data handling can be generalised and documented through accompanying policies. The preferred approach to managing data is typically communicated at the beginning of a project, either verbally or in writing, and is conveyed to subsequent doctoral candidates during their onboarding. An example of such a policy can be found from the Daumann Group at: <https://www.cup.lmu.de/ac/daumann/erc-starting-grant-lanthanophor/research-data-management-plan/>

Section: Data Description

Question Set: Content Data Description

Question: How does your project generate new data?

Help: Research data is typically generated in every research project. Here, you should reflect upon and describe the ways in which you generate research data. The methods of data generation may vary depending on your specific chemical subdiscipline. Consider the methods and tools you use.

Research Data Management Organiser

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Feedback Language ▾

<https://rdmo.nfdi4chem.de/>

(accessed 2025-12-09)

Templates:

- Chemistry-specific DFG checklist
- Horizon Europe DMP
- Software Management Plan
- RDM policy generator

Welcome to RDMO

The tool enables researchers in the research domain of chemistry to create a data management plan (DMP) for their research project. After logging in with and one time activation of your DFN account you can choose from several templates that guide you through the different aspects of a DMP.

NFDI AAI with Reg-APP

We appreciate your feedback

helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de

Maintenance window

Tuesday 6:30 am - 8:30 am

Figure: Screenshot of the [RDMO instance of NFDI4Chem](https://rdmo.nfdi4chem.de/) from 2025-12-09

Sections of our DMP template

Section 1:
Data description

Section 2:
Documentation and data
quality

Section 3:
Storage and technical
security during the project

Section 4:
Data exchange and long-
term data accessibility

Section 5:
Legal obligations and
conditions

Section 6:
Responsibilities and
resources

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Hands-on: Create your own DMP

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Section 1

Data description

Administrative data

- **DMP version:**
 - Date of first version
 - Date of last update

- **Project information:**
 - ID
 - Project name
 - Funder
 - Grant reference number
 - Project description
 - Name and ID (e.g., ORCID) of principal investigators and main researchers
 - Project data contact
 - Related policies

Section 1: Questions

Content data description

- What kind of dataset is it?
- How does your project generate new data?
- Is existing data reused?

Technical data description

- Which data types (in terms of data formats) arise in your project?
- And in what way is the data further processed in your project?
- To what extent do these arise or what is the anticipated data volume?

A legal definition (Directive (EU) 2019/1024):

“[...] documents in a digital form, other than scientific publications, which are collected or produced in the course of scientific research activities.“

BUT: not always digital (e.g. documents, objects, samples)

DFG (2015):

"Research data include measurement data, laboratory values, audiovisual information, texts, survey data, objects from collections or samples that are created, developed or evaluated in scientific work. Methodological test procedures such as questionnaires, software and simulations can also represent central results of scientific research and should therefore also be included under the term research data. "

Research data in chemistry

Data format standards

Introduction to file formats: Video

Data format standards

- Unencrypted, uncompressed, unpatented/non-proprietary, standardised, ideally open

Caution: open \neq non-proprietary

- If data is stored in a proprietary format (format of original software), it should always be stored in an open/archivable format as well, if possible.

Data type	Recommended	Not recommended
Table	CSV, TSV	XLS
Text	TXT, TEX, ODT, HTML, RTF	DOC
Video	FFmpeg, OpenH264, Xvid	MPEG-2, MPEG-4, MVC
Image	PNG, SVG	GIF, JPG, PSD, AI, PUB
Audio	WAV, FLAC, OPUS	WMA, MP3

Table: Adaption of table “Open Formats of Open Source Software” by [Roman Gerlach](#) et al. licensed under [CCO](#) via [Zenodo](#) (adapation: NFDI4Chem style, re-ordering)

Data format standards in chemistry

- Recommendations for data format standards and converters can be found in the [NFDI4Chem knowledge base](#).

Analytical method	Proprietary file extensions	Converter to open file format	File format
NMR spectroscopy	.fid, .mnova	MNova Topspin	JCAMP-DX, nmrML, NMReDATA
Mass spectrometry	.raw, .d, .baf,	Proteowizard	mzML
IR spectroscopy	.ispd, .icIR		JCAMP-DX
UV/vis spectroscopy	.dsw, .str, .bsk, .bkn, .ksd	proprietary software	comma-separated values (.csv)
HPLC	.xls	proprietary software	comma-separated values (.csv)

Self-working phase

1. Go to RDMO to start writing your own DMP
2. Create a new project by using [+New project](#)
3. Add a title and a short description
4. Choose the [NDFI4Chem_Template](#) as catalog
➔ Create the project
5. Click on [Answer questions](#)
6. Define one dataset for your project
7. Answer the questions in the section [data description](#)

Discussion

Which aspects of defining your dataset were most challenging for you?

Did you find it difficult to define the scope or boundaries of your dataset?

Does the template provide all the answers you need for your project?

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Section 2

Documentation and data quality

Section 2: Questions

Documentation

- What approaches are being taken to describe the data in a comprehensible manner (such as the use of available metadata, documentation standards or ontologies)?
- What digital methods and tools (e.g. software) are required to use the data?

Data quality

- What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality?
- Are quality controls in place and if so, how do they operate?

Naming conventions

PRO TIP: NEVER LOOK IN SOMEONE ELSE'S DOCUMENTS FOLDER.

Figure: "Documents" by [xkcd](#) licensed under [CC BY-NC 2.5](#) via [xkcd.com](#), accessed: 2025-12-09

README

- A README is a simple text (.txt) or markdown (.md) file
- Contains metadata about data and/or folder structure, e.g. naming conventions, data types
- Very flexible and easy to use and reuse
- Makes your data more understandable and easy to get into
- Content may vary depending on the purpose
 - Internal documentation
 - Accompanying document for data publication

What is metadata and why is it important?

- Data that describes data
- Makes datasets searchable (and findable)
- Makes datasets understandable and FAIR
- Machine- and human-readable
- Standardisation is ongoing

Figure: “Data for future generations” by [Auke Herrema](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [RDM Promotional Material](#)

Metadata schema and standards

Metadata Schema

- Determines and structures the metadata elements
- Pairs of [metadata element - value](#)
- Defines input type
- Sets restrictions, such as the use of (controlled) vocabulary or required fields

Metadata Standard

- Schema that have undergone a review process
- Usually in their respective community
- Common examples: ISO, DIN, and EN standard

International Data Exchange format

- Describes digital or physical web resources
- 22 elements – 15 with an ISO certificate
- Refinements and encoding schemes for subject specific applications
- For more information:
 - <http://www.dublincore.org/>
 - <https://www.dublincore.org/resources/userguide/>

Controlled vocabulary

- An organised arrangement of words with a defined scope
- Promotes consistency and allows the variability of used terms as well as context and relationships

Example: Use of CHMO ontology in Chemotion

TFE-237 | 1-0 | Decoupled | Inventory

$C_{12}H_{12}O_3S_2$
ethyl 5-phenylthiophene-2-sulfonat
e

268.351880 g/mol
Exact mass: 268.022786 g/mol

CAS select or enter

View in 3D

Properties | Analyses | QC & curation | References | Results

Edit mode | Order mode | Add comment | Analyses from upload | + Add analysis

1H NMR Add to Report View in 3D Share Print Close

Type: 1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)
Status: Confirmed ¹H count: 0/12 Instrument: 0/1
Content:

Name	Status
1H NMR	Confirmed

Type (Chemical Methods Ontology)

1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)

Content

Normal | B | I | U | X₂ | X² | EA | H | IR | UV | MS

Description

Figure: “Class tree of CHMO showing 1H NMR” as depicted by [NFDI4Chem Terminology Service](#) (id:CHMO:0000593), accessed: 2026-01-04

Chemotion ELN

IUPAC, InChI, SMILES, ✎ ✕

by analysis type | 1h n | 🔍 ✕

1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)

Samples | Schematics

What is an ELN?

Basic System (not an ELN)

- Text entries
- Attachments
- Annotation
- Search function
- Sharing via the cloud

e.g. Evernote, GoogleDrive, Dropbox, MS Sharepoint

Electronic Lab Notebooks

- + Structured metadata in human- and machine-readable formats
- + Templates
- + Discipline-specific functions/ editors
- + Basic inventory management
- + Rights management
- + Audit trail
- + API (Application Programming Interface)

e.g. Labfolder, eLabFTW

High end systems

- + Customer relationship management (CRM)
- + Inventory management
- + Workflows
- + Link to lab equipment
- + Analysis and data mining
- + Electronic signatures
- + Reporting or statistics modules

e.g. Limesophy LIMS

Advantages of an ELN

Avoid Data Loss

- Linking experimental descriptions to collected data (analog and digital)
- Secure data storage, backups

Standardised Documentation

- Structured and standardised collection of metadata
- Generation of interoperable (meta)data

Knowledge Management

- Data are findable
- Data are accessible
- Data are available, even after change of personnel!

Publication

- Data provision for publication of research results
- Simple transfer of data to repositories

How to choose an ELN?

- There is no one „ELN to rule them all“
- How can one ELN cater to the needs of a whole university?
- Need to select the right ELN for the job

Browse • Team About Log In

ELN Finder

The ELN Finder helps you to search and select a suitable Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN) for your purposes.

- More than 40 filter criteria available.
- Filter criteria clearly divided into categories.
- Result list of the identified ELN tools displayed in an overview.
- Brief descriptions of the individual tools included.

[Find your ELN by using filter criteria](#)

Latest changes

active
NuGenesis
Waters Corporation; Waters distributes software, equipment (e.g. chromatography) and laboratory accessories under various brands

Figure: “Website ELN Finder”
accessed: 2026-01-04

Self-working phase

1. Go back to your RDMO project
2. Answer the questions in the [documentation and data quality](#) section for the one dataset you created earlier on

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the self-working phase?

Did you find the answer options sufficient to complete the template?

Are data quality and control measures already established at your site?

Break

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Section 3

Storage and technical security during the project

Section 3: Questions

Data storage during the project

- How is the data to be stored and archived throughout the project duration?
- How are the generated or existing physical samples linked to the data during the project's duration?

Technical data security during the project

- What is in place to secure sensitive data in this dataset throughout the project duration (access and usage rights)?

Different types of data preservation

- **Active data**
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept short-term
- Purpose: Protection and discovery

Backup

- **Final Data**
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept long-term
- Purpose: Preservation of information

Archiving

- **Final Data**
- Open access
- Data persistence depends on the publishing institution
- Purpose: Provision of data for reuse

Publication

Common causes of data loss

Hardware error

Accidents & disasters

Malware & hacking

Software error

User error

Loss & theft

Interested in more?

[Research Data Scary Tales of TKFDM](#)

Figure: Adaptation of “CompFrontSmall” by [pyroclastichawk](#) licensed under [CC BY 2.0](#) via [flickr](#) (adaptation: picture is cropped)

Criteria for selecting data storage (1/2)

1. Storage space & place (physical & virtual)

- Availability of required data volume
- How many storage locations and devices am I using?
Keep this number low!

2. Backup plan

- Backup frequency (daily, weekly)
- Number of copies needed
- Automation
- Storage duration
- Full vs. incremental vs. differential

Criteria for selecting data storage (2/2)

3. Versioning

- Need to keep track of different versions?
- Manually vs automatically (e.g. git)

4. Access & Security

- Shared access (e.g. collaborators, remote working?)
- Protection against manipulation and loss (password needed?, encryption?)
- Legal constraints (e.g. data privacy)

5. Responsibility

- Am I in charge? Or my IT support?

Lifespan of storage media

- Lifespan of storage media is restricted
- New hard drive storage every 2-5 years

The 3-2-1 rule for backups

Use the possibility of an automatic backup!
Regularly check the backup for recoverability and readability!

Data versioning

Why is it important?

- Traceability (tracking of changes with timestamp and user ID)
- Reproducibility of workflows
- Facilitates collaboration
- Possibility to reset to previous version if necessary

The screenshot displays the GitHub interface for the repository `CSSEGISandData/COVID-19`. The repository has 1,290 commits, 8 branches, and 0 tags. The commit history shows recent updates to files like `archived_data`, `csse_covid_19_data`, `who_covid_19_situation_reports`, `.gitignore`, and `README.md`. The README section is titled "COVID-19 Data Repository by the Center for Systems Science and Engineering (CSSE) at Johns Hopkins University" and describes the repository's purpose for the 2019 Novel Coronavirus Visual Dashboard.

Figure: <https://github.com/CSSEGISandData/COVID-19> (accessed 2025-11-04)

Data versioning: manual vs automatic

Manual versioning

- Use file naming convention to document file version (v01, v02,...)
- Use archive subfolder for older versions
- Create and maintain versioning table to document all changes to data (and documents)
 - File name, date of change, author, comment on what was changed

Automatic versioning

- Changes are automatically tracked
- Facilitates collaborative work on data and documents
- Built-in functions (e.g. cloud services)
- Use specific version control software

Technical data security

Certain types of research data require special protection due to legal, commercial, or contractual reasons.

- Personal data
- Patents
- Industry collaborations
- Confidential and sensitive data

- Access and usage rights
- Confidentiality agreements/ Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs)

Rights and role management (1/2)

- Ensure that **access rights** are clearly defined and documented:
 - Who has access to what, and who determines this?
 - Who determines which access rights users have?
 - Who is responsible for maintaining access rights (i.e. granting and revoking them)?
 - How often are access rights reviewed?
 - Which data require access rights?
 - How and where should the above be documented?

Rights and role management (2/2)

- Use strong passwords!
 - <https://help.lafayette.edu/guidelines-for-strong-passwords/>
- Use password managers
 - e.g., [KeePass](#)

Group work

Breakout session

Discuss the following aspects in your group and make notes on the provided whiteboard:

- Suitable storage solutions
- Linking options for data and physical samples

Self-working phase

Answer the questions in the [storage and technical security](#) during the [project](#) section.

Consideration: Do the answers provided in the template match the solutions you discussed earlier in the group work?

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the group work / self-working phase?

Are the results of your group work similar to the answers in the template?

What additional options have you identified?

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Section 4

Data exchange and long-term data accessibility

Section 4: Questions

Reuse

- Is this data set especially suitable for use in other contexts?
- Which criteria are used to select research data to make it available for subsequent use by others?
- When is the research data available for use by third parties?

Archiving

- How do you archive your data and in which suitable infrastructure?
- Are embargo periods to be observed? If so, how long are they?
- How are the physical samples archived, and how are data linked to the physical samples?

Restrictions on publication

- Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility?

What is a licence?

- A licence is a contractually agreed right of use.
- It is granted by the copyright holder to another party to use the copyrighted work in specific ways,
 - to copy it,
 - to modify it,
 - to make it digitally accessible
 - or to use it commercially.

Licences and their openness

Licence model	Processing prohibited	Commercial use prohibited	Copyleft	Attribution	Copyright waiver / waiver of rights to enforcement
Creative Commons	CC-BY-NC-ND, CC-BY-ND	CC-BY-NC-SA, CC-BY-NC	CC-BY-SA	CC-BY	CC0
Open Data Commons			Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL)	Open Data Commons Attribution License	Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and License (PDDL)
Community Data License Agreement			CDLA-Sharing-1.0	CDLA-Permissive-2.0.	

restrictive
open

Different types of data preservation

- **Active data**
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept short-term
- Purpose: Protection and discovery

Backup

- **Final Data**
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept long-term
- Purpose: Preservation of information

Archiving

- **Final Data**
- Open access
- Data persistence depends on the publishing institution
- Purpose: Provision of data for reuse

Publication

The 4 steps of data preservation

1. What to keep? Data selection
2. How to keep? Prepare data and files for the preservation
3. Where to keep? Suitable location or medium
4. Perform periodic checks of the preserved data

Reasons for data publication

Figure: By [Brian Hole](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [figshare](#)

FAIR principles

According to the DFG's guidelines on good research practice, research data must be FAIR!

DFG GRP Code of Conduct Guideline 13

Providing public access to research results:

*"[...] whenever possible **researchers make the research data and principal materials on which a publication is based available in recognised archives and repositories in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).**"*

How can I publish my data?

Supplement of an article in scientific journal

The screenshot shows a journal article page with a dark header. The main content area features a section titled "Supplementary files" with a yellow "Download this article" button and a blue "Article HTML" button. Below this, there is a section for "Supplementary information" and "Article information". The article title is "Alkyne-tagged imidazolium-based membrane cholesterol analogs for Raman imaging applications".

Data Journal

A collage of logos for data journals and platforms. At the top left is "GENOMICS Data". To its right is "(GIGA)ⁿ SCIENCE". Below these are "RMets" (Royal Meteorological Society) and "Geoscience Data Journal". In the center is "Nuclear Data Sheets". To its right is "DATA SCIENCE Journal". Below that is "Biodiversity Data Journal" (A peer-reviewed open-access journal). At the bottom left is "Journal of chemical & engineering data". At the bottom center is "WILEY ONLINE LIBRARY" and "SCIENTIFIC DATA".

Data Repository

Data repositories

Dataset
+ Metadata + PID

Generic

Domain-specific

Institutional

Data repository selection criteria

- Long-term availability (Certification?)
- Provision of a PID (e.g. DOI, URN, ARK)
- Licence (e.g. Open Access, Restricted)
- Domain-specific or institutional
- Data curation options

re3data.org is a helpful tool for finding a suitable data repository.

Figure: Adaptation of “Figure 2. The re3data.org icon system” by Heinz Pampel et al. licensed under [CC BY 3.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/) via [PLOS ONE](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0151111) (adaptation: figure is cropped)

Breakout session

Discuss the following aspects in your group and make notes on the provided whiteboard:

- What strategies exist at your site for the backup, archiving, and publication of your research data?
- Have you ever published your data in a repository?
If so, did you choose a generic or domain-specific repository?

Self-working phase

Answer the questions in the [data exchange and long-term data accessibility](#) section.

Consideration: Do the answers provided in the template match the strategies and ideas you discussed earlier in the group work?

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the group work / self-working phase?

Did you find the answer options sufficient to complete the template?

Have you identified additional answer options in your group / on your own?

Lunch

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Section 5

Legal obligations and conditions

Section 5: Questions

Legal restrictions

- What is in place to consider aspects of use and copyright law as well as ownership issues?
- What are the legal specifics associated with the handling of research data in your project?

Scientific specifics

- Are there any significant research codes or professional standards to be taken into account?

Disclaimer

- This session is designed for informational purposes only and does not substitute legal consultation.
- We assume no liability for the accuracy of the information presented.
- The NFDI has established a section to work on legal aspects in research data management.
- For any concrete questions on legal aspects, contact the legal office of your university or research institution!

Research data policies

- Guidance on how to handle research data
- Provide an overview of
 - Responsibilities for research data management
 - Available infrastructure and support services
- Different types of policies required by

Source: https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/jikjlb2g/se_rdm_best_practices.pdf (accessed 2025-10-26)

Source: <https://www.forschungsdaten.info/praxis-kompakt/english-pages/guidelines-and-policies/> (accessed 2025-10-26)

Source: <https://www.dfg.de/en/research-funding/funding-initiative/research-data/recommendations> (accessed 2025-10-26)

DFG “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” (2019)

- Fundamental revision of the recommendations from 1998
- Modifications:
 - Multidimensional approach
 - Codex with 19 guidelines
 - 11 guidelines on the research process
 - RDM is relevant in 8 of these 11 guidelines

Figure: “Structure of the DFG Code of Conduct Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” [Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft](#) licensed under [CC BY-SA 4.0](#) via [Zenodo](#)

Who “owns” research data?

You can own only physical objects!

No ownership of data!

You can own the rights on the data, in case they are part of another protected right (e.g. copyright, patent law, business secret).

Why learn about copyright?

Disseminate with
maximum visibility

Properly reuse
other's data

What are protected works?

- UrhG §2, §4
- “Only the author’s own intellectual creations constitute works within the meaning of this act”

Literary works
(written works,
speeches)

Computer
programms

Musical works

Pantomimic and
dance work

Artistic work,
including works
of architecture

Cinematographic
works

Photographic
works

Illustrations of
scientific or
technical nature
(maps, plans,
tables)

Collections and
databases

Copyright requirements

Individuality

Must be a personal creation or be derived from personal choices of its maker.

Originality

Must show a certain level of originality, i.e. exhibit a degree of creativity, which exceeds standard or routine effort.

Content	Individuality	Originality	Copyright protected?
Computer programs (e.g. a specific simulation)			
AI generated (e.g. ChatGPT)			
Raw data from scientific instruments			

Public domain of research results

1 “Scientific content, research results, theories, concepts, ideas, facts, formulae or findings are not licensable as such, as they are in the public domain.”

2 “They may therefore be used by anyone for any purpose.”

3 “Nobody can prohibit another person from using existing knowledge. [...] it is never possible to commit ‘theft’ of scientific content [...].”

4 “[...] scientific works only enjoy copyright protection because of their form of presentation, but not because of the ideas, findings and results they contain.”

There is no copyright on (unprocessed) research data!

Picture of the molecules and reaction

Tabulated properties of experimental materials

Formula	Mol mass	Mass [g]	Volume [mL]	Density [g/mL]	mmol	Equiv/yield
4-fluorobenzaldehyde (4-fluorobenzaldehyde)						
S C7H5FO	124	2.00	1.73	1.16	16.1	1.00
ethanamine (ethanamine in Wasser)						
R C2H7N	45.1	1.65	2.04	0.810	24.2	1.50
Potassium carbonate (K2CO3)						
R CK2O3	138	2.23	0.00	0.00	16.1	1.00
tetrabutylazanium;bromide (reactant)						
R C16H36BrN	322	1.56	0.00	0.00	4.83	0.300
4-(ethylamino)benzaldehyde (SG1-V2448-A)						
P C9H11NO	149	0.181	0.00	0.00	1.21	8%

Solvent(s):

Brief description of the experiment

Description:

4-Fluorobenzaldehyde (2.00 g, 1.73 mL, 16.1 mmol, 1.00 equiv), ethanamine (66% 1.09 g, 1.35 mL, 24.2 mmol, 1.50 equiv), tetrabutylazanium;bromide (1.56 g, 4.83 0.300 equiv) and Potassium carbonate (2.23 g, 16.1 mmol, 1.00 equiv) were stirred over a period of three days. Water was given to the reaction and the resulting mixture extracted three times with ethyl acetate. The combined organic phases were washed with brine and dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered.

Type of Purification: Flash-Chromatography

Dangerous Products:

TLC control: Rf-value: 0.67 (Solvent: cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 1:1)

Additional information for publication and purification details:

As preparation for the column chromatography (dryload), silica gel was added (6 g) and the mixture of combined organic phases + silica gel were evaporated. The obtained crude product was purified via flash-chromatography on silica gel using cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 4:1

Analysis:

[C9H11NO](#) (CHMO:0000593) | 1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃ [7.27 ppm], ppm) δ = 9.73 (s, 1H), 7.72–7.68 (m, 2H), 6.62–6.60 (m, 2H), 4.37 (br. s., 1H), 3.26 (q, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 1.30 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 3H).

[C9H11NO](#) (CHMO:0000595) | 13C nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (13C NMR)

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃ [77.0 ppm], ppm) δ = 190.2, 153.3, 132.3 (2C), 126.4, 111.7 (2C), 37.9, 14.5.

[C9H11NO](#) (CHMO:0000630) | infrared absorption spectroscopy (IR)

IR (ATR, ν) = 3291, 2967, 2923, 2870, 2852, 2809, 2731, 1661, 1586, 1570, 1566, 1562, 1545, 1534, 1508, 1498, 1474, 1451, 1437, 1427, 1395, 1378, 1366, 1342, 1310, 1283, 1231, 1147, 1109, 1062, 1044, 997, 824, 810, 634, 619, 590, 583, 510, 426 cm⁻¹.

[C9H11NO](#) (CHMO:0000470) | mass spectrometry (MS)

EI (m/z, 70 eV, 60 °C): 149 (100), 134 (99). HRMS (C₉H₁₁ON): Calcd 149.0835, Found 149.0835.

Analysis of the measurement data

There is no copyright on (unprocessed) research data!

Picture of the molecules and reaction

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Solvent(s):

Copyright FREE

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Analysis of the measurement data

Copyright

In general:

- Raw research data is not protected by copyright.
- You need to check whether your data meets the requirements to be protected by copyright.
- If it is protected by copyright, then there are different author rights.

When does data protection play a role?

What kind of data is collected?

A) Data without personal reference:
Data protection is not relevant!
This is the typical case in chemistry.

A) Data with personal reference (e.g. interview, survey, video recordings, human samples):
Data protection is relevant!

What is personal data?

Legal basis:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- German Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG)
- Data protection laws of the federal states
- Area-specific data protection law and statute law

Definition:

- Art. 4, GDPR: “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’). An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly”
 - e.g. name, age, address, location data, IP address
- In addition: Special categories of personal data (“sensitive” personal data)
 - e.g. racial or ethnic origin, political opinion, processing of genetic data, health data, sexual orientation

Processing of personal data

Processing:

- Is generally **prohibited** except

- a law permits it **or** persons give informed consent
- Take care of specific data security requirements (e.g. storage place and time, access)
- Consider technical measures like pseudonymisation, anonymisation

Data protection law relevant for doing research, also project settings can require confidentiality!

Self-working phase

1. Go back to your RDMO project
2. Answer the questions of your DMP in the [legal obligations and conditions](#) section

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the self-working phase?

Do you know any other significant research codes or professional standards?

Who can help you answer any unclear questions of this section?

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DATA.

Section 6

Responsibilities and resources

Section 6: Questions

Responsibilities

- Who is responsible for the appropriate handling of research data (description of roles and responsibilities within the project)?
- Who is responsible for curating the data after the project's duration?

Resources

- What resources (costs, time or other) are required to implement appropriate research data management in the project?

ORCID and ROR ID

- ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)
- Globally recognised registry for the identification and connection of researchers and their research activities
- Increasingly being used for verification purposes when registering for certain research-related tools and services
- Linking between ORCID and other author ID schemes possible
- <https://orcid.org/> - get your own ORCID!
- Research Organization Registry (ROR) - <https://ror.org/>
- Global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organisations containing associated metadata (e.g. type of organisation, website)

https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/docs/pid/

Cost factors

- Existing RDM expertise (personnel costs are often the biggest factor at 70% +!)
- Data volume
- Heterogeneity/complexity of data types
- Sensitive data (effort for anonymisation/pseudonymisation/obtaining consent)
- Required computing power and required data connection/interfaces
- Licence fees
- Usage and access model
- Compliance with legal obligations (e.g. acquisition of special furniture/software for data security/data protection)

OpenAIRE guide on estimating RDM costs:
<https://www.openaire.eu/rdm-costs/>

Costs - DFG

Project-specific costs are funded:

- Preparation of research data for connection use
- Transfer of research data into existing infrastructures
- Personnel costs
- Project-specific hardware and software
- User fees (e.g. infrastructures)
- So-called INF projects in SFBs

BUT basic equipment is not funded!

Group discussion

Breakout session

Discuss the following aspects in your group and make notes on the provided whiteboard :

- How are responsibilities managed at your site?
- Are you able to estimate the (personnel) costs and efforts for implementing appropriate research data management?

Self-working phase

1. Go back to your RDMO project
2. Answer the final questions of your DMP in the [responsibilities and resources](#) section

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the group work / self-working phase?

Did you find the answer options sufficient to complete the template?

Were there any similarities in your group's answers to the questions?

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Additional functionalities

Q&A Session

What questions do you have?

„Homework“ and follow-up Q&A session

- Optional homework:

You filled in the DMP template for one dataset during the workshop. Complete your DMP for your whole project in the upcoming weeks.

- Follow-up Q&A session:

Any questions left or new ones arising during the homework? Join our **follow-up Q&A session on XX.XX., XX-XX am/pm** (invitation follows).

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Wrap-up

NFDI4Chem service portfolio

All chemists publish FAIR data

That is our vision. To get there, we will support scientists in their efforts to collect, store, process, analyse, publish and re-use research data in chemistry. NFDI4Chem develops and maintains a national research data infrastructure for the research domain of chemistry in Germany, and we enable innovative services and science based on research data.

NFDI4Chem is a DFG-funded non-commercial consortium from the community for the community.

Visit our website:

<https://www.nfdi4chem.de/>

What can we do for you?

Click on a category below to find out more about our work!

Electronic Lab Notebooks

Chemistry Repositories

Knowledge Base

Terminology Service

Helpdesk

Search Service

Contact & Helpdesk

Looking for contact information or help on research data management, data repositories or electronic lab notebooks (ELN) for chemistry?

Get in touch with us!

Task Area	Lead	Project Manager
1 Management	Christoph Steinbeck	Franziska Ebert
2 Smart Lab	Nicole Jung	Adam Basha
3 Repositories	Felix Bach & Matthias Razum	Christian Bonatto Minella
4 Standards	Steffen Neumann	N.N.
5 Community & Training	Sonja Herres-Pawlis & Johannes Liermann	Jochen Ortmeyer
6 Synergies	Oliver Koepler	Johannes Hunold

Helpdesk

Contact our consortium-wide Helpdesk to get advice and support on most topics related to research data management, data repositories or electronic lab notebooks (ELN) for chemistry.

Send an email to helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de

Single point of entry to support you with all questions you may have regarding research data management.

For example:

- Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs)
- Data Management Plans (DMPs)
- FAIR Data

helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de

Selection of other services by NFDI4Chem

NFDI4Chem Stammtisch
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& ensures consistency

Repositories
FAIR, discipline-specific
& open

Dataset Search Service
efficient, focused
& easy-to-use

and much more ...
www.nfdi4chem.de

Evaluation

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Thank you for participating in the evaluation!

QR code

[Link to the evaluation](#)

Acknowledgement

This workshop is inspired by the materials of

- Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management
(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4071471> / <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773203>)
- Research Data Management Team Friedrich Schiller University Jena
- Research Data Management Team RWTH Aachen University
- TU9 German Universities of Technology
(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3466206>)

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(unless stated otherwise on specific slides)

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Thank you for your attention!